

DARE UK

SATRE – Standardised Architecture for Trusted Research Environments

Final Report

October 2023

UK Research
and Innovation

HDRUK
Health Data Research UK

ADRUK
Data-driven change

SATRE

Final Report

1. Executive Lay Summary

The SATRE DARE UK-funded Driver Project was challenged to create a trusted research environment (TRE) architecture supporting the research community's need to have suitable data analytics and research environments for working with sensitive data. The project developed an inclusive and transparent way of working to ensure that what was created was representative of the TRE community in the UK.

We have created, for the first time, an open specification for TRE operators by which to evaluate themselves against a set of capabilities. It is a thorough specification, perhaps definition, for TREs informed not only by the experience of the project team who have been running a TRE and supporting sensitive data projects for a combined 15 years, but also the expansive knowledge of the wider UK research community. The public have also been involved throughout the development of the specification to ensure their voices are heard and reflected in the specification.

The specification has been informed through one survey completed by 105 individuals representing approximately 60 organisations, 14 Collaboration Cafés with up to 75 participants, 26 individuals contributing directly, 44 issues raised and six public engagement sessions online and in-person. Despite the breadth and diversity of the individuals included we have been able to create a single specification encompassing four architectural principles, four pillars, 29 capabilities and 160 statements. The 75 mandatory statements are what are considered the minimum required to be a SATRE compliant TRE.

Now with a stable version 1.0 release the specification is ready for use by the UK TRE community. We are and will continue to work with all organisations to evaluate themselves against the specification and also identify what works and what doesn't, which will be captured in future versions of the specification.

The specification has been developed for the long-term in mind and can be a basis for a common understanding between operators, data controllers, accreditors, researchers, industry and government organisations for how TREs can federate and interoperate better.

2. Project Outputs

2.1. The SATRE Specification

The formal SATRE specification is a living document hosted at <https://satre-specification.readthedocs.io/>. It provides a resource for TRE operators and builders to standardise their TRE services and infrastructure according to the contained guidance. It is suitable for both existing and in-development TREs.

The specification has an easily navigable structure and hosts the specification via GitHub pages. It is written in markdown and "readthedocs" format.

The specification contains a set of TRE capabilities, which are broken down into statements - such as under the "Document and SOP Management Process" capability:

“You must ensure that changes to policies and standard operating procedures can only be made by trusted individuals.”

Each capability statement is designated as **Mandatory**¹, **Recommended** or **Optional** and includes accompanying guidance explaining how a TRE operator or builder might ensure this capability is met by their TRE.

When writing the specification, the team began by discussing and classifying what the broad areas of TRE provision were and decided on a model where TRE capabilities were grouped into four pillars:

1. **Information Governance**; including capabilities related to quality management, risk management, training delivery and various other aspects of governance
2. **Computing technology and Information Security**; e.g. end user computing experience, infrastructure management and information security
3. **Data Management**; e.g. output management, identity access management and data lifecycle management
4. **Supporting Capabilities**; e.g. financial management, public engagement and project management

The specification also contains an evaluation process which TRE operators can use to identify oversights in their TRE design and determine what work could be done to bring their TRE into line with the specification’s recommendations. This involves reading and determining whether (and how comprehensively) the TRE meets each of the capabilities.

2.1.1. How was the specification format and content decided upon?

At the start of the project, the SATRE team did some exploratory comparative work on three open-source reference implementations of TREs, which they were familiar with from deployments at their home institutions. These were Azure TRE², TREEHOOSE³, and The Alan Turing Data Safe Haven⁴. This work included attempts to compile a list of common TRE features and understand the ways the TREs differed in their technical architecture and user experience.

Based on the initial comparisons between these TREs, and their own prior experiences of building and operating them, the team conducted a survey to solicit opinions from TRE builders and operators on many key aspects of TRE design and functionality. The survey responses informed the initial stage of development for the specification.

It was decided that the ultimate contents of the specification should be compiled not just by the SATRE team, but the broader TRE community in the UK as well. The SATRE team decided that all work contributing towards the specification content should be performed openly and publicly.

To enable this, a contribution model (see section 2.5.2) was carefully developed whereby the web page content could be easily edited in markdown format. Anyone can submit content suggestions via GitHub issue templates and maintainers can easily introduce these changes and suggestions to the specification pages after discussion has taken place inside the issue via GitHub’s comment feature. Using GitHub also means the specification is under version control and could be hosted online even whilst under active development.

The contribution process either involved GitHub issues being drafted by interested parties who were aware of SATRE and wanted to have input, or more often by the project team from internal discussion or sourcing

¹ Some of the public involvement statements are Mandatory if the TRE involved the use of personal data.

² <https://github.com/microsoft/AzureTRE>

³ <https://github.com/HicResearch/TREEHOOSE>

⁴ <https://github.com/alan-turing-institute/data-safe-haven>

comments from *Collaboration Cafés* (see section 2.5). The specification was developed iteratively, with feedback from an increasingly diverse range of TRE stakeholders as the project progressed.

For the TREs hosted at The Alan Turing Institute and The Health Informatics Centre, University of Dundee, the SATRE team carried out a full evaluation (see 2.3 Evaluation below). These evaluations were completed with version 1.0.0 of the specification and the results are included with the specification for full transparency and to guide others. According to the scoring system that was developed, both TREs included all the mandatory capabilities and can be considered SATRE compliant. Through the evaluation process both found improvements that could be made.

In addition to the specification and evaluation pages, the specification has a clear landing page, a contributions page, FAQs and a glossary.

2.1.2. Response and lessons learned

Specification requirements were initially gathered via a survey⁵ sent out to TRE builders and operators. Whilst many useful suggestions were made, the design of the survey proved to be too granular and encouraged responses that were too specific, rather than capturing the general needs of TRE builders and operators. The survey did not reflect the capability-based approach that was adopted for the specification later. Despite this, it provided a useful starting point for discussions and encouraged early involvement from a broad cross-section of the TRE community.

Early in the project it became apparent that a formal SATRE technical specification would be less valuable than general guidance, and the overwhelming feedback from the TRE community was that guidance around information governance (IG) was a priority. The project team responded by including IG as the first pillar in the specification. This was a good example of the community engagement sessions (see section 2.5) which were consistently positive, with contributions to the specification from a variety of individuals from across the TRE community.

Building the specification from the ground-up was a good way to ensure that the overall technical structure of TREs was captured. However, initial drafts of the specification had a quite low-level focus, and felt tied to specific TRE implementations, risking becoming too much like a checklist of technical features. Adopting a higher-level view of how TRE elements linked together and the reasoning behind the need for these technical features was key to building the specification.

2.2. Specification Architecture

SATRE provides a comprehensive high-level architecture for research organisations handling sensitive data safely. The formal architecture definition is documented using the ArchiMate⁶ modelling language with models created using the open-source modelling tool Archi⁷. A detailed description of the architecture is described elsewhere together with a download of the ArchiMate source files⁸, however, an overview is provided here.

The SATRE outputs are broken down into four layers (as represented in Figure 1):

1. Scope: definition of a TRE,
2. Capabilities: abilities an organisation needs to run a TRE,
3. Components: people, processes and technology needed to deliver the capabilities

⁵ https://github.com/sa-tre/feature_survey

⁶ <https://pubs.opengroup.org/architecture/archimate3-doc/>

⁷ <https://www.archimatetool.com/>

⁸ <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.8411273>

4. Specification: how to run those components safely.

SATRE Structure

Figure 1. The high-level structure of SATRE outputs.

The architecture output primarily deals with capabilities and components defining what an organisation needs to deliver a TRE. This architecture provides a comprehensive high-level component design enabling research organisations to handle sensitive data safely. Capabilities an organisation requires to run a TRE are documented and deconstructed to show the elements (roles, processes, applications and data) needed to realise those capabilities.

Figure 2. Meta-model used to document the architecture.

Figure 2 shows the meta-model where processes, data, roles and applications combine to provide the capabilities needed within an organization to fulfil requirements for each of the SATRE four pillars (see section 2.1). The SATRE architecture and associated models are intended for use by designers and builders of trusted research environments including research infrastructure developers and enterprise and solution architects.

This architecture will serve as a tool to:

- Help implementers design and implement environments within a variety of organisations using a mix of existing and novel technologies.
- Provide insight into the underlying components of a TRE and allow improvement planning and road mapping.
- Provide a common understanding of the component elements of a TRE, what functionality they provide and how they fit together to the TRE user community.
- Facilitate the communication of how one or many TREs function alone or together through federation.
- Build end-user tools to help interrogate the specification and evaluate themselves against the specification.

2.3. Evaluation

The SATRE specification has been defined, and in order for TREs to assess themselves against it an evaluation mechanism has also been defined. All the capability statements, regardless of whether they are mandatory or not, are considered by the TRE organisation and they can score themselves against the scoring matrix in Table 1. The matrix was intentionally designed to be readily understandable and easy to apply.

Table 1. Scoring matrix for specification self-evaluation.

Score	Description
0 (Not met)	The TRE does not meet this requirement (if this is Mandatory this means the TRE is not SATRE compliant)
1 (Sufficient)	The TRE meets this requirement but there is substantial scope for improvement
2 (Satisfied)	The TRE meets this requirement but there may still be scope for improvement
N/A (Not applicable)	Not applicable: The statement is not relevant to a TRE, may apply to Recommended or Optional statements and a very limited number of Mandatory* (see 2.6.2 for details) statements.

The evaluation process was evaluated by [The Alan Turing Institute](#) and [HIC TREs](#), with input from TRE personnel who were not involved in the development of the SATRE specification. With the aim of full transparency, the results are included as part of the specification as an example for others to follow. The process helped find areas where the specification was unclear or could be improved, to consider different circumstances under which certain specification statements may or may not apply, and to generally improve the experience of completing the evaluation. This also led to the creation of a downloadable spreadsheet⁹ for evaluation, which encourages TREs to provide written explanations and possible improvements, something that is particularly useful for understanding how a particular TRE is operated.

The recommendation is for TRE organisations to do the evaluation as a team exercise including individuals with knowledge of all aspects covering the four pillars, and for it to be a discussion point around what is missing, what may need improvement, or new features to consider. A guidance estimate of 1-2 days of FTE is appropriate to complete the evaluation.

2.4. User testing and a TRE usability principle

⁹ <https://satre-specification.readthedocs.io/en/stable/satre.xlsx>

Users are critical stakeholders of TREs as highlighted in the *DARE UK Federated Architecture Blueprint*.¹⁰ Standardised architecture could positively impact the work practices of thousands of TRE users across the UK. While the DARE UK Blueprint provides an entry point into understanding some user roles, we wanted to know more about who TRE users are, the kind of work they do, and how well-built TREs can better meet their needs. In order to achieve this, the SATRE team conducted a series of engagements with TRE users over the course of the Driver Project. We describe the contributions made by TRE users and their implications in a full report separately - *Trusted Research Environment users. Evidence supporting a TRE usability principle*.¹¹

This report contributes to the SATRE project in two ways. First, we provide a rich set of recommendations that builders and operators of TREs can follow to increase TRE usability. We encapsulate these recommendations in a TRE usability principle which is incorporated in SATRE's specification architecture version 1.0. Second, we outline the methods and analytic perspectives we have used to understand users' needs and we recommend a series of future research ideas now required to advance this work. We summarise relevant points from this report herein.

2.4.1. New insights into understanding TRE users and usability

The central contribution of our work on users and usability is to show that usability is both a technical property of TREs (that can be standardised and implemented at scale), and a sociotechnical characteristic that emerges in specific contexts of use and is influenced by users' needs, existing knowledge, skills and prior experiences. This has important implications for future design and evaluation work that aims to improve TRE usability. Most significantly, it indicates that compliance with a standard architecture should be complemented with contextual guidance, informed by evidence about a diversity of local TRE users. In documenting our engagements with users – through group discussions, observations and formal user testing sessions, we recommend ways in which such evidence might be produced.

The work also differentiates four user types common across different organisational and regulatory settings such as universities, healthcare and industry. These are analyst-researchers, TRE operators, data research managers (who typically line-manage teams of analysts), and information governance users charged with compliance responsibilities. We use these user types to structure recommendations relevant directly to TRE operators and TRE builders.

The evidence base for our work on a usability principle was compiled through observations made at four sets of structured interactions with different kinds of TRE users across the UK. Observations and unstructured conversations with data analysts took place during a week-long Data Study Group on-site at The Alan Turing Institute in London. Following that, two 90-minute dialogue sessions were convened online, where a diversity of TRE users discussed their experiences working with TREs and working with other TRE users. Users and usability were the focus of discussions at two Collaboration Cafés run by the SATRE project. Finally, a set of real-world user experience sessions were organised at Ulster University to assess the experience of first-time TRE users. These sessions were designed to assess and compare high-level usability in terms of system familiarity and levels of difficulty experienced when running a defined set of data analysis tasks across two TRE implementations.

2.4.2. TRE user experiences and the need for further user research

Our user experience (UX) testing experiments revealed usability issues with the two TREs we used. Issues included, but were not limited to, incoherence between novice users' mental models of what good research

¹⁰ The DARE UK Blueprint outlines prospective development pathways for the DARE UK federation of TREs. See DARE UK Delivery Team. (2023). *Federated Architecture Blueprint*. DARE UK (Data and Analytics Research Environments UK). <https://dareuk.org.uk/our-work/federated-architecture-blueprint/>

¹¹ See *Trusted Research Environment users. Evidence supporting a TRE usability principle at* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10056074>

environments should be like, and their experience of actually using a TRE; difficulties locating data to be analysed; data egress functionality; and logging out of the systems. From this, several recommendations are relevant to this report:

- Onboarding and documentation needs to acknowledge the conceptual leaps that novice users need to make when first transitioning from their day-to-day working environment to TREs.
- Labelling and signposting is an area where significant usability gains can be made.
- Diverse methods of user testing should be a feature of all future TRE research and development.
- Research and development on TRE usability should engage with operators, data managers and TRE analyst-researchers to identify comprehensive improvements in UX for tooling, infrastructure and standards as well as communications and user support. This work must better understand users' expectations and mental maps of TREs as well as their needs.
- Producing knowledge about users' workflows and what they perceive as gaining and losing by using TREs is critical. As is understanding how users' tasks, roles, and jobs are changing as a result of TRE use. In the long term this will have important implications for safe trustworthy research culture, job satisfaction, well-being and training.

Our intention is that this work helps TRE decision makers not only understand the needs of their users, but also balance those needs with commitments to robust and reproducible science, as well as information governance and compliance. Our user report will also provide a critical first step for planning how and where to direct support for new or migrating TRE users. Specifically, whether trade-offs between safety, security and productivity might be best addressed through standardisation or technical changes to TREs on the one hand, or on the other, through alternative means, such as training, the provision of ongoing support, interventions in organisational rules or practices or by other means entirely.

A final broader point is relevant here. Many technical solutions have been designed and built during the DARE UK Driver Programme. Given the time constraints however it was not possible to adequately consider user experience within the projects or across the programme. Now, building on the significant stakeholder engagement by the SATRE team and across DARE UK, future work must engage operators, data managers and TRE analyst-researchers to identify comprehensive improvements in UX for tooling, infrastructure and standards, and to fill gaps in knowledge identified throughout our work with TRE users.

2.5. Stakeholder Engagement

SATRE is a community-led and owned specification, and its development, governance and sustainability have and will require comprehensive and inclusive stakeholder engagement. The ethos and goals were for the specification to be developed transparently in the open and to ensure it reflected the views and needs of all those involved in the development and use of TREs, thus ensuring its adoption and utility.

2.5.1. Stakeholder Activities

To these ends we carried out a set of activities, from initial stakeholder scoping to an ongoing programme of open Collaboration Cafés.

The initial focus of this work package was to identify the different stakeholder groups we wanted to engage, and what method of engagement would work best for them. Table 2 describes the four stakeholder groups that interacted with the SATRE project.

Table 2. SATRE stakeholder groups and their characteristics.

Stakeholder Group	Characteristics
HDRUK Health Data Research UK	
	ADRUK

TRE Strategists	Anybody who is at a policy, regulatory, funding or otherwise strategic position for TRE provision. They have significant decision-making influence in the TRE space, including the ONS and the NHS
Builders/operators	Those who are responsible for building or managing TRE provision in their own organisations
Information Governance professionals	Those responsible for overseeing the safe management of data at their organisations
Users, or Analyst-researchers	Those who have to use TREs for research purposes, simply called users at the start of the project. Characterised as Analyst-researchers through User Research (see 2.4)

The project team developed an engagement plan adapted to each group:

- **Feature survey:** While this exercise was very informative for the starting work of the project, receiving over 100 responses from across academia, industry, healthcare and government, it resulted in a level of technical detail that was not of interest to the community; it was especially useful though in establishing a communication channel with stakeholders and realising the need for the project to start considering Information Governance as a stakeholder group, and to include it in the remit of the specification.
- **Targeted discussions:** one-to-one conversations were conducted mainly with TRE Strategists at the beginning of the project to better understand what national bodies would expect of a specification for TREs. This included the NHS, ONS and the Digital Economy Act (DEA) team at UKSA. Through these conversations we explored how we could best utilise SATRE in each context. Whilst not fully embedded, there is energy for the NHS SDE technical design to be SATRE compliant, and for the SATRE specification to live alongside the DEA as a more granular example of good TRE provision. Embedding these relationships will be undertaken by the SATRE Working Group (see section 4).
- **Kick-off sessions:** early in the project we held two kick-off sessions to present the project, its aims and proposed methods of engagement. These were attended by over 75 people across many institutions and marked the start of a continuous community engagement. These were instrumental in setting a solid foundation for our co-creative, community approach to our work from the very beginning.
- **Collaboration Cafés:** following on from the kick-off sessions we established fortnightly Collaboration Cafés on the first Tuesday and third Thursday of the month. Having them scheduled from the beginning of the project ensured continuity, allowed people to plan, and scheduling on different days facilitated attendance. These were consistently attended by 20 to 40 people and became the backbone of stakeholder engagement. Each café would be dedicated to a specific theme for feedback and contributions to the specification where discussions would directly impact its development. Discussion points were turned into GitHub issues so attendees could see their opinions directly reflected and having an impact. The full schedule, topics and links to notes have been archived¹². All 44 discussion issues arising from stakeholder engagement or team discussion about the specification are openly available in the specification repository¹³.
- **Survey share out:** after processing results and carefully removing any identifying information results were shared during a Collaboration Café on 18 May. This café was the 4th in the series and the first with a specific and clear topic shared in advanced. The success of this café demonstrated the importance of providing specific topics and asks to the community in order to increase participation.

¹² <https://github.com/sa-tre/satre-notes>

¹³ <https://github.com/sa-tre/satre-specification/issues?q=is%3Aissue++label%3A%22discussion+point%22+>

- **Evaluation sessions:** these sessions were the last activity of this project phase and served to encourage organisations to evaluate themselves and share results, this will allow to create a repository of best practices and allow the specification and any subsequent standards to be further influenced by the TRE Community.
- **UK TRE Community day roundtable:** We also ran a session in the breakout discussion section of the UK TRE Community day in early September to explore and discuss the governance of the SATRE specification, which informed our approach as laid out in 4.1.1. This further engaged relevant members in the community in the ongoing development of SATRE and showcased our commitment to continuing maintenance and ownership of the specification beyond the funding window.

2.5.2. Structure for Engagement

In addition to the above activities, it was necessary to provide the right infrastructure, processes, and guidance to make contributions not only possible but accessible, and the project as a whole open. Participatory engagement within the project was a core need of the project. This included creating non-technical ways of contributing (through Collaboration Cafés, email or via a structured form¹⁴), a guide for contributing directly through GitHub¹⁵, and blog posts sharing regular updates about the project¹⁶.

The extent to which we worked openly is reflected in the various communication channels we established:

- GitHub Project organisation - to host both the specification and project plans developed in the open for everyone to see, comment and contribute. The GitHub Organisation contains the following resources:
 - Specification repository: live and open to contribution for the development of the specification <https://github.com/sa-tre/satre-specification>
 - Project management repository: open project activities <https://github.com/sa-tre/satre-team>
 - Public backlog and roadmap <https://github.com/orgs/sa-tre/projects/1>
 - Public notes from the SATRE project: <https://github.com/sa-tre/satre-notes>
- Medium page - published blogs on the project activities and outputs in an accessible way <https://medium.com/satre>
- Collaboration café - event schedule and open notes https://github.com/sa-tre/satre-notes/tree/main/collaboration_cafes
- All SATRE project outputs and resources have been published on DARE UK's Zenodo community¹⁷

GitHub is a technical platform and presented a barrier to participation for non-technical people, for this reason a lot of time and care was put into simplifying processes and guidelines were prepared. The guidance available within the specification on using GitHub and markdown for collaborative notes is an output in itself that can and will be reused¹⁸. On top of that we dedicated time in each Collaboration Café to address challenges and help attendees make contributions. See Section 2.6 for more on public engagement.

2.5.3. Outcomes of Stakeholder Engagement

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<https://forms.office.com/Pages/ResponsePage.aspx?id=OTEYrjoJKk2Bpl0zS82QGQQh5LWVvyKJMjCf72dnH9PNUOUwzMIJWUFEExQVBDRVBEOVIWRjY5UjVUSi4u>

15 <https://satre-specification.readthedocs.io/en/latest/contributing/walkthrough.html>

16 <https://medium.com/satre>

17 https://zenodo.org/communities/dare_uk

18 <https://satre-specification.readthedocs.io/en/stable/contributing/index.html>

The stakeholder engagement programme allowed the project to receive feedback and respond rapidly. The contents, delivery and usability of the specification was shaped by this exercise, making true our aim to be community led.

We have worked on shared projects across the DARE UK ecosystem, most notably collaborating on a shared glossary for [key TRE terms](#) to ensure we use the same concepts and language across all projects. This was the topic of another collaboration café in which attendees directly edited and contributed to it.

Participation and contribution was wide and meaningful. There is an underestimated active list of all people who have contributed to the specification¹⁹. At least 25 people outside the project team made direct contribution. This is an underestimate as more participated in Collaboration Cafés that informed changes to the specification, and some have opted not to be formally named. Individuals representing about 60 different institutions, from universities to funding bodies or different working groups within the NHS, have been part of the ongoing attendees to our engagement activities.

Collaboration cafés were central to receiving community input throughout the project. They shaped much of what we have done from feedback in these cafés, including:

- Specifically focusing on information governance as a specific pillar for this project
- Adapting how we write the architecture from being feature focused (too specific) to capability focused
- Adopting community-driven principles and considerations that govern the use of the architecture
- Changing the methods of evaluation for TREs to compare themselves against the specification
- Getting requests for targeted feedback from certain communities (i.e. useMyData for our public engagement principles, see 2.6)

2.5.4. Lessons learned

The project and its activities have allowed us to learn along the way. We have learnt many key lessons that we will apply to any following project we take part in, and we hope are of use to the wider DARE community. These include:

- *Working in the open works*: being able to point people to where activity is happening and allow people the chance to directly contribute to issues and content has allowed us to live and breathe collaborative research. Being open and transparent by default made the project able to move quickly.
- *Collaboration is easier when there is a specific task*: in the early stages of the project, our approach to collaboration was more ‘what do you think of this broad idea’, which we realised is quite difficult to quickly and concisely answer in collaborative spaces. We changed to an approach of creating/developing something (say, content for the architecture), and asking for specific feedback on it. This led to more productive conversations, and allowed us to pinpoint where our approach has been misaligned with community wants and needs.
- *Making the most of limited time*: expecting people to voluntarily spend time reading through the entirety of our outputs and submit changes was unreasonable. Much more effective was short, sharp and direct engagements (for instance, through collaboration cafés), that provided a clear window of time in which people could contribute.
- *Strategic collaboration matters*: it is of fundamental importance to work together with the community to build impactful, representative research. It is also crucial to ensure those with decision making authority are brought into the collaboration too – a lot of feedback we have received on whether our work will be useful is whether those who set standards will advocate for it. Thinking strategically about who to engage,

¹⁹ <https://github.com/sa-tre/satre-specification/blob/main/README.md#contributors>

and when (as you don't want to say 'believe us' without having anything to 'believe' in) has been an important lesson to learn.

2.6. Public Involvement and Engagement

A separate report has been submitted covering the details of the public involvement and engagement (PIE) in the SATRE Driver Project. Here, a summary of the report will be described.

PIE was embedded in SATRE from the very start of proposal planning. We had existing PIE relationships from the previous GRAIMATTER and TREEHOOSE DARE UK projects which we were able to use to develop a PIE work package.

2.6.1. Approach

Upon project initiation we had a PIE coordinator and two public members on the team to ensure that PIE was embedded throughout the project with the aim of ensure the public voice was included. This was particularly challenging in this technical project as the topic itself could have been a barrier.

The strategy was to identify the needs and concerns of the public regarding trusted research environments at the start of the project, use that information to adapt the specification and then feedback to the public how the project responded.

We also developed a programme of outputs specifically for a more public audience. This included a SATRE Medium blog²⁰, infographics to share with the public at in-person events, and an informational video on TREs and the SATRE project. The video was commissioned with an external company and the artifacts shared with the TRE-FX team for use in their project.

2.6.2. Impact on Specification

The initial public sessions at the start of the project identified aspects of cybersecurity, oversight and transparency as key issues for the two focus groups we engaged with. In response the specification included specific sections on Cybersecurity and IG, plus two statements in Section 4.8 of the specification include requirements for engaging with the public to include transparency and public oversight.

The follow-up sessions near the end of the project showed the draft specification to the participants with specific focus on the PIE-relevant statements. Overall, the participants had positive opinions on the statements, however, almost universally a strong opinion was that they should be mandatory for all TREs and not optional as they currently were.

Mandatory inclusion of PIE for TREs was problematic as some may only be involved in commercially sensitive data rather than personal data, meaning that engaging with the public was less relevant. Therefore, a compromise of a "Mandatory*" category was created where if a TRE used personal data then they should include the public statements.

2.6.3. Lessons Learned

Success of Public Members on Project Teams: this is an approach used across many projects and successful in ensuring the public voice is embedded. This is reliant on the public members role being clear and a good top-down approach to including them in the project as equals. They attended regular project meetings just like anyone else in the project.

²⁰ <https://medium.com/satre>

Value of building on existing and concurrent work: with a broad topic that SATRE has there is much existing knowledge and work on public perspective and building public trust which can be used to inform the output meaning they do not rely on just small pockets of engagement. This means the engagement can be focused on the wording and nuance of the SATRE guidelines.

Challenges of recruitment to sessions: recruiting public participants can be tricky, in future a more strategic approach with external agencies combined with taking advantage of *ad hoc* opportunities could be beneficial as well as longer projects which are able to avoid the disruption of summer holidays.

Communications Expertise: working with a communications person to plan and manage the video output utilises existing expertise within the partner organisations and ensures a public output.

Involving PIE professionals: this is a network of people with a wealth of knowledge and experience on public thoughts and are experienced at advocating for public voices and views in projects.

Accessible routes to engage with other work packages and directly integrate the public views across the Driver Programme. Significant more impact could have been delivered by combining forces especially given that members of the SATRE PIE team was also involved in TRE-FX and SARA.

3. Impact

We have delivered the first open specification for UK TREs which has been informed since the start by the UK TRE community and the public. Over 40 individuals representing over 60 organisations have been involved in informing the SATRE specification.

26 direct contributors to the specification with many more indirect contributions from people involved in discussions during Collaboration Cafés.

Well established TREs from the Health Informatics Centre with over 10 years' experience and The Alan Turing Institute with over five years' experience have fully evaluated themselves against the specification. These evaluations have been made public and show how they can continue to improve.

UCL is developing a new TRE and will be using the specification as a basis for it.

Several existing TREs have either already started evaluating themselves or have committed to doing so. We have established a mechanism for sharing evaluations within the community.

Extensive support and expansion of visibility for the UK TRE Community which has grown substantial over the SATRE project. It has matured and has received DARE UK community funding to continue its work and maintain some aspects of SATRE.

The public was clearly and explicitly included in a technical specification for TREs ensuring their voice was heard. Indeed, a particular patient group – useMyData – requested to have session with the project team which we ran a Collaboration Café and was well received.

The activity of Collaboration Cafés was very successful in bringing external stakeholders into the project and, importantly, keeping them engaged.

Open and transparent scientific research is effective, accepted and has low overheads. It ensures a legacy for the project that can be seen for years to come.

€5m HORIZON 2020 funding awarded for the EOSC-ENTRUST project which is aiming to apply TRE knowledge and expertise from the UK to wider European partners. SATRE is mentioned as an exemplar. Led by Elixir UK Hub with

collaborators including HDR UK, University of Nottingham and University of Manchester plus partners from 16 European countries.

4. Contribution to DARE Phase 2

Now that an informed and credible specification for TREs has been created for the first time, Phase 2 needs to harness not only the document, but also the community that has developed around it. There is an engaged and interested group of valuable members of the UK research environment around sensitive and personal data.

The SATRE specification needs continuity and ownership for it to be widely accepted or recognised by data controllers and the research community. We will continue as much as possible within the UK TRE Community to keep momentum moving, although there are other priorities within the community. This work will be undertaken by a working group within the UK TRE Community led by Dr Christian Cole and including individuals from the University of Dundee, The Alan Turing Institute, UCL and others. Initially, governance and contribution frameworks for the specification, building upon SATRE’s existing methods, will be formalised by this working group. The group will meet fortnightly to maintain the SATRE specification, continue fostering contributions from the community and further embed the specification across institutions and contexts. This work will be supported by the UK TRE Community Management team, as part of their commitment to supporting community projects through the DARE UK Community Groups funding.

With a growing list of TREs which have self-evaluated against the specification DARE UK has the opportunity to involve them in further development activities during Phase 2. The specification can be used as a compliance gateway for access to DARE UK Phase 2 projects as collaborators or interested parties thereby ensuring a minimum standard as well as an acceptance of common interests.

The formal architectural patterns which can now be built on top of the specification allows the creation of tools supporting interrogation or semi-automated evaluation of TREs. New design patterns, as shown in Figure 3, can be created as part of Phase 2 to encompass specific functionalities such as federation (as developed by TRE-FX or Teleport), disclosure control (from SACRO) and data provenance (from SARA) developing an ecosystem for UK TREs to engage with.

Figure 3. Extending the SATRE specification.

Longer term, and as part of a wider project which may include outputs from the other Driver Projects, there needs to be commitment to the establishment and maintenance of the standards of a Trusted Research Environment (TRE) as an ongoing process rather than a one-time event is paramount. Adoption of the specification by major UK accreditation authorities or data controllers would ensure rapid up-take by groups and organisations. The UK TRE Community Working Group will continue to establish this links ahead of Phase 2. In today's rapidly evolving digital landscape, where data privacy, security, and ethical considerations are in constant flux, the static nature of a one-time assessment would be inadequate. To ensure the relevance and effectiveness of TRE standards, it is imperative to review and update these standards at regular intervals, ideally every three years. This periodic reassessment ensures that the standard controls remain pertinent, aligned with industry best practices, and capable of addressing emerging challenges.

Ultimately, the SATRE specification is an output of the wider community, not just the SATRE consortium, and is a response to frustration within the community over the proliferation of different TREs. A frequent request is for SATRE to be accredited or approved by a major public body- this is something we'll pursue, and evidence of a significant number of evaluations will help build the case.

5. Alignment with DARE UK Federated Blueprint

The DARE UK Federated Blueprint is an "initial" proposal for a UK federation to support the use and reuse of sensitive data in research projects. We are of the opinion that the SATRE specification aligns well with the blueprint. The SATRE architecture intentionally references where the internal architecture of a TRE interacts with the federated blueprint (as shown in Figure 4). This was intentional as we were aware of the policy context that SATRE and the other DARE UK Driver Projects sit within following the publication of several influential reports from the NHS, UK Government and HDR UK.

Figure 4. SATRE architecture interacting with the DARE UK Blueprint.

Specifically, the SATRE architecture and specification align with the blueprint particularly by linking conceptual and infrastructure layer aspects and providing a functional entry point for TRE operators to engage with a future UK federation. The flexibility of viewing and interacting with the SATRE architecture means that a conceptual view can be used to map on the DARE concepts and an infrastructure view can support mapping design patterns for individual services as required by either the specification or the blueprint.

Furthermore, the SATRE architecture can be used to identify the component gaps that may exist within and between TREs when attempting to move to the federated blueprint. Some examples in the above model such as the user onboarding process, identity verification and user identity attributes would need to be aligned in some

way to reach the goal of federation. In this way the SATRE architecture can be used to design, plan and implement changes required for federation while being inclusive of other DARE UK or new capabilities.

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